

Function $f(n)$ Prime Numbers

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Abstract :

This Function $f(n)$:

$$f(n) = 1 + (n * (4 * n + 5)) = N$$

If $\frac{N}{n+1} = \text{integer}$

this mean $(n + 1)$ is a prime number

Example:

$$n = 36$$

$$f(n) = 1 + (36 * (4 * 36 + 5)) = 5365$$

factors of 5365 are $5 * 29 * 37$

$$\frac{5365}{36+1} = 145 \text{ is an integer}$$

this mean $(36 + 1) = 37$ is a prime number

Conclusions :

Verification in update